

Charles Stuart's Will, drawn up by his lawyer, Mr. Palmer, in Bengal Will 1828, Parts 3 & 4, pp. 213-224.

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Stuart's Will of 9 September 1823, with a codicil of 24 April 1825, revised on 17 April 1827 and in March 1828.

Exhibit A, referred to in the annexed affidavit of Palmer John sworn the 28 day of August 1828 before me.

In thus making my last will and testament, I, Charles Stuart, Major General in the Honble East India Company Service on the Bengal Establishment, do give and bequeath as follows, viz.:

- £ 5.000 To my Brother, Thomas Stuart of Limerick in the Kingdom of Ireland, five thousand pounds sterling,
- £4.000 To my Sister Eliza, wife of Captain Baker of the Armagh Militia, four thousand pounds sterling,
- £3.000 To Mrs Mary Stuart, relict of my Brother John Stuart, to be equally divided between her heirs Children, three thousand pounds,
- £300 To Mrs Charlotte Freeman, relict of the late Dr Freeman of Bengal, three hundred pounds sterling,

[over the above is written]

Superseded by a new arrangement as per accompanying schedule Cha. Stuart March 1828.

- £300 To Eliza, the Indian born daughter of my friend Walter Macquire, formelly of the Bengal Civil Service, three hundred pounds sterling,
To Mr Daniel Watson of Gort in the Kingdom of Ireland [added] NB. dead without heirs, and to his Sister Catherine fifty pounds sterling each [the word 'each' later stroked out]
- £200 To Mrs Charlotte Nelly, wife of my friend Lieut. Colonel John Nelly formerly of The Bengal artillery, one hundred pound sterling and to her husband the said Col. Nelly (my School fellow), one hundred pounds,
- £100 To Mrs Sarah Ochterlong, a widow and daughter to my friend Lt Colonel Nelly aforesaid, one hundred pounds sterling,
- £50 To Hannah Kitchin of Cheltenham, fifty pounds sterling, NB. this sum already advanced by my agents in London,
- £150 John Foster brothers Denis Neale of Quarter Town near Nallow in Ireland and to his two Sisters, fifty pounds each sterling and to their heirs,

£200 To the four Sisters of my friend the late Dean Burke of Gort in Ireland, viz.
Catherine, Mary, Jane and Bridget, fifty pounds sterling each and to their heirs,

[over the above is written] Superseded by a new arrangement

£200 To lieut Colonel D.V. Kerin of the Bengal Establishment should he survived me,
Sicca Rupees Two thousand or two hundred pounds Sterling

[crossed out and beside is written] Dead without heirs.

After discharging other legacies to Indian Servants as per separate list, the residue of my property to be equally divided between the children of my late Brother Thomas and my Sister Mrs Baker, aforesaid, and of my late brother John. As my executors in Europe and hereby appoint my Brother Thomas aforesaid and Lt Colonel John Nelly before mentioned now residing at N° 3 lower Gardiner St, Dublin.

I also hereby appoint John Palmer, Esqr. of Calcutta of the firm of Palmer & Co., my sole executor in India, having the most perfect confidence in his honor and integrity. I have property in the hands of my European agents Mefsr's Pacton, Cockerell, Trail & Co. of London.

Also in the hands of Messrs Palmer & Co. and of Alexander & Co. of Calcutta my Indian statues of stone alabaster, copper brass et al, Indian spears, swords, shields, dagger, India picture[s] and other curiosities, to be sent to England to the care of Messrs Pacton & Co., aforesaid, to be disposed of at the discretion of my Europe executors and to be cover'd by my Insurance for the voyage home to the amount of thirty thousand Rupees.

[in the margin] The much mutilated statues not to be sent to Europe. NB, see codicil 24 th Apl 1825.

I have an extensive Library, numerous Indian Pictures et al and other articles all in London under charges of Mr John Rodwell, bookseller, Bond Street who receives twenty pounds per annum for the care of them. My executors will dispose of them for the advantage of my Estate. Messrs Pacton & Co. have charge of some small trunks &c of mine such Hindoo images as they may contain, are to be presented to Richard Gregory, Esqr of Berners St & of Coole Lodge in Ireland should he survive me (otherwise to be sold off).

£100 To John Nelly, the son of Lt Colonel Nelly, aforesaid, I bequeath one hundred pounds sterling.

Charles Stuart

Berhampoor in Bengal,
the 9th September 1823.

[crossed out] Codicil: such statues, pictures, swords, shields, dagger and furnitures et al as I have lodged in my house N° 1 Wood Street, Chowringy in Calcutta are to be disposed of in one lot with the house, should the six Boxes containing female ornaments of silver, gold & jewels &c be not previously disposed of or sent to England they are all to be disposed of by auction in six lots.)

Calcutta, 24th April 1825:

The statues and other curiosities at Berhampoor to be sent to England as afore mentioned.

NB: all now in Calcutta

NB: Revised 17th April 1827 & March 1828.

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EXHIBIT B referred to in annexed affidavit of John Palmer sworn the 28 day of August 1828 before me.

Donations to servants as per separate paper referred to in my will dated 9th September 1823.

Raghoo Nauth Sing
Twelve hundred dicca Rupees.

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Charles Stuart
Major General
9th September 1823
Berhampoor
NB. All India claims to be paid off immedly by Mr John Palmer & Co..
Confirmed 7th Sepr 1828

Mefsr Palmer & Co. after paying all Indian legatees will remit the balance of my Acct with them to Mefsr Cockerell & Co. of London to be at the call of my Europe executors.
NB. The money advanced (above four hundred pds) to Henry Robert Addison for removal to the cavalry in England to be excused.
I bequeath to Mrs Lucy Addison to her daughter Lady Sheridan & her younger daughter Mrs Colette McPherson, two hundred pounds each, also to Mfs Trelawny daughter, to the late Caroline Addison, two hundred pounds.

Charles Stuart

Donations to servants referred to in my will. 9 th September 1823.

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EXHIBIT C referred to ni annexed affidavit of John Palmer sworn the 28th day of August 1828 before me.

For the Indian House Museum

Sun Dial	from Calinger
Large Vismu	Luckey Serai
Boar Avatar	B(adoh) P(athari) near Bhilfa
Sculptured slab	Dif. as Pr D°
Indra	Burgaun Behar
Cali large	Bobun Ifsur Orifsa
Surfutti	
Sculptured slab	Bobun Ifsur D°
Ditto Door Posts &c	Simroun
Ditto Bull and black Lingam	Calingar and Bengal
Reclined Goddess &c	Bundle Cd (Bundelkund)
Buddha figure (sandstone)/ lions supported	D°
Elephantal figure	Urdungee Benares
Brahma & consort	« Calinger
a Sutti Pillar with inscription	Bhilfa

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EXHIBIT D referred to in annexed affidavit of John Palmer, sworn the 28 day of August 1828 before me.

I bequeath
March 1828

To my Sister & to the wo widows of my Brothers John and Thomas and the third Childern (about one and twenty) ... total, twenty pounds each, five hundred pounds Total twelve thousand pounds
£12.000

.....
[here follow some additional bequests of money]

In the Supreme Court of Judicature at Fort William in Bengal,
Eclesiastical Side
In the goods of Charles Stuart decaesed.

John palmer of Old Fort Street in the Town of Calcutta, Agent and Member of the Firm of Meffrs Palmer and Compagny, Maketh Oath and Saith, that the paper writings here into annexed and marked respectvelly with the letters A B C and D, contain as he, this deponent, verily believes the last will and testament and two several codicils to the last will and testament of the above named Charles Stuart late, a Major General in the Service of the United Compagny of Marchants of England Trading to the East Indies on their Bengal Establishment, deceased and that he, this deponent, is the sole Executor appointed by the said Will and this deponent further Saith that he, said Charles Stuart who was in his life time a British Subject, hath lately departed this life at Calcutta leaving effect with the jurisdiction of this honorable Court to be administred.

Sworn the 28 dy of August 1828 before me.

John Palmer

Rep. 28th August 1828
E. Ryan